

ISic1437

I.Sicily inscription 1437

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Megara Iblea

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330372

1. Φιντύλος □ ηουγρίτο⁻²⁶ ὁ Εὐγρίτου = ὁ Εὐκρίτου(?)²⁶ τὰν στάλαν τάνδ' ἀνέθε⁻κε.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644980

PHI 330372

Bibliography

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Arena, R. 1996. Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.12

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